

Source: [Heravi, M.M.](#), Mirsafaei, R., Hosseinnejad, T., Ahmadi, S. (2016), Copper(II) nanoparticles: an efficient and reusable catalyst in green oxidation of benzyl alcohols to benzaldehydes in water, Journal of Applied Organometallic Chemistry, 30(10), [doi: 10.1002/aoc.3509](https://doi.org/10.1002/aoc.3509)

Copper(II) nanoparticles: an efficient and reusable catalyst in green oxidation of benzyl alcohols to benzaldehydes in water

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Razieh Mirsafaei, Tayebeh Hosseinnejad, Shervin Ahmadi

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Copper(II) nanoparticles immobilized onto 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) supported on mesoporous silica KIT-5 nanocomposite (AK) was prepared. The APTES group on KIT-5 was manipulated as a suitable coordinating agent for copper(II) and fully characterized using FT-IR, SEM, EDX, ICP, TGA, XRD and UV–visible methods. Moreover, a quantitative description for metal–ligand interactions in the APTES-KIT-5 mesoporous silica-supported copper(II) acetate complex was assessed via quantum chemistry computations. This novel transition metal supported heterogeneous surface was used as an effective catalyst in low loading for selective oxidation of differently substituted benzylic alcohols in water, using H₂O₂ as oxidant to give the corresponding carbonyl compounds in high to excellent yields. This heterogeneous nanocatalyst can be recovered and reused several times without any significant loss of activity.

Keyword

density functional theory, Nanocatalyst, oxidation in water, Carbonyl compounds, Catalysts, Copper, Nanoparticles, Oxidation, Quantum, chemistry, Quantum theory, Silica, Transition metals, 3 aminopropyltriethoxysilane, Coordinating agents, Heterogeneous surface, Metal-ligand interactions, Nano-catalyst, Quantitative description, Quantum chemistry computations.